

Data files for phylogenetic analyses in Downey et al. (2021)

Filename	Description
trimal-script.txt	trimAl command for alignment trimming
amas-script.txt	AMAS command for alignment concatenation
iqtree-script.txt	IQTREE command for phylogenetic analysis
partitions.txt	partitions for IQTREE analysis
LSU.afa	LSU d1/d2 alignment, untrimmed
SSU.afa	SSU alignment, untrimmed
psbC.afa	psbC alignment, untrimmed
rbcL.afa	rbcL alignment, untrimmed
LSU-trimmed.afa	LSU d1/d2 alignment, trimmed
SSU-trimmed.afa	SSU alignment, trimmed
psbC-trimmed.afa	psbC alignment, trimmed
rbcL-trimmed.afa	rbcL alignment, trimmed
concatenated-trimmed.afa	final concatenated alignment
iqtree.tre	Newick-formatted phylogram with bootstrap values
spicaticribra-tree.pdf	full tree figure

Reference Downey KM, Julius ML, Theriot EC, Alverson AJ. Phylogenetic analysis places *Spicaticribra* within *Cyclotella*.